

Global reach and local context: the impact of bilinguality on online search

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Search engines, social media and various chatbots are used across the globe daily (Haider & Sundin, 2019; Pires et al., 2019). Users approach these platforms through an array of languages. The use of multiple languages on platforms is not only due to the vast geographical reach of the platforms but also users' proficiency in multiple languages. Statistics from the EU show that in 2022, 90 percent of working-age adults with a high level of education knew at least one foreign language. The same survey shows that 28 percent of working-age adults in the EU who knew at least one foreign language stated that they were proficient in their best-known foreign language (Eurostat, 2022). Furthermore, English is spoken by about half of Europeans (Eurostat, 2024). Language proficiency, or lack thereof, may enable or hinder access to vital information. Previous research indicates that among minorities in various countries, a lack of language proficiency in the official language may impact access to health information (Nzomo et al., 2021).

This short paper presents the outlines of a study currently under development. As search engine results are affected by factors such as language use (Lewandowski, 2023), I am interested in how people who are bi- or- multilingual navigate online search in relation to various topics. With the project I am interested in questions such as: how do people who are bi- or -multilingual make use of their language skills when searching online; are certain topics associated with specific language use; what topics are searched for using mother tongue versus foreign language? The term online search is here used in a broad sense and may include the use of search engines, chatbots as well as social media. The project is intended to take place in Sweden where circa 20 percent of the population were born in another country than Sweden (SCB, 2025). This means that a significant number of the population have another mother tongue than Swedish. This is another aspect which is of interest to the project; how do people who have another mother tongue than the national language of the country in which they reside, navigate the use of various information channels? Ranging from online search of information pertaining to news as well as civic information. A topic of great societal importance, not least in relation to crisis and critical societal situations in which the government aims to communicate with the entire population. The Covid-19 pandemic highlighted the importance of people staying updated with information communicated by various national agencies.

I intend to investigate the topic through interviews with people who are multilingual and residing in Sweden. Various digital methods might also be used to investigate differences between search results depending on language use and specific topics as previous research indicates that language can have an impact on search results (Graham, 2023). The overall aim of the project is to shed light on the impact of bilingualism on online search in everyday life.

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